

DESIGN, ANALYSIS AND TESTING OF AN INTEGRALLY STIFFENED
COMPOSITE CENTRE FUSELAGE SKIN FOR FUTURE FIGHTER AIRCRAFT

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ABSTRACT

The skin is a one piece carbon fibre composite monocoque with double curvature and is stiffened with simultaneous cured frames and longerons. In this paper the basic design, the material selection and the stressing of typical features will be discussed and compared with test results. The given design will finally be assessed on weight saving and production cost aspects.

Keywords: Composites; Composites Application; Design Methodology

1. INTRODUCTION

The constant demand for improved performance in the development of new fighter aircraft requires substantial weight reductions in the structure. Besides improvements in the design and analysis techniques (e.g. integrated design, optimization) carbon fibre composites together with advanced construction methods, like cocuring of skins and stiffeners in one cure cycle, offer a significant weight saving potential.

2. DESIGN

For manufacturing reasons the fuselage is split into three major components, the front, the centre and the rear fuselage. The centre fuselage (Fig. 1) has a length of about 4.9 meter and a width of 2.2 meter. It is characterized by the ducting of the engine air intakes above which the structure is more or less continuous and forms the boundary of the centre fuselage integral fuel tanks. Under the constant demand to reduce the weight of fighter aircraft this upper skin portion is best suited to be produced from carbon fibre reinforced plastic. The lower portion of the centre fuselage has large cut-outs for nose and mainlanding gear and mainly contains the aircraft systems which require access for maintenance purposes and the load carrying structure there is rather inhomogenous. Because of high and concentrated load introductions and on battle damage reasons most of the internal structure of the centre fuselage is built from aluminium alloys.

Based on comprehensive trade-offs with respect to weight, produceability and access to internal structure and equipment, the upper skin is designed as a one piece continuous part with circumferential frame stiffeners and four integrated longerons. This CFRP structure is mounted to the bulkheads, two shear walls on top of the intake ducts and side tank floors by means of mechanical fasteners.

The monocoque has to

- carry part of vertical and lateral shear and corresponding bending as well as torsion and internal fuel pressure and external aerodynamic loads,
- to react loads introduced from other aircraft components e.g. front, rear fuselage and wing and internal centre fuselage equipment.

The four longerons - two on the top and one per side - together with the skin are carrying end loads resulting from bending moments. These end loads are varying from - 78 kN to +190 kN. The longerons (Fig. 2) are built by interleaving unidirectional layers between the basic skin plies. The number of longeron layers and thus the corresponding thickness varies between 5.75 mm and 9.5 mm and is adjusted optimally to the loads. At the interface to front and rear fuselage the longerons are thickened up to accommodate for larger diameter bolts at attachment fittings. The width of the additional unidirectional layers decreases with distance to the outside contour forming a ramp. To prevent drastic stiffness changes this ramp has a ratio of 1 over 10 between the unidirectional plies.

The skin (Fig. 3) is basically designed to carry bending, shear, torsion proportionally and the local pressure loads. Hoop stiffening frames are equally placed at a pitch of about 200 mm to prevent buckling of the skin below limit load, to redistribute shear, and to carry part of the pressure loads. The skin thickness varies between 2.75 mm at the forward end and 3.75 mm at the rear end. The skin is built with plies in 0/90 and ± 45 degree direction with 0 degree axis in flight direction. Skin lay up and ply orientation is optimized for strength and stiffness with engineering concessions to achieve a produceable laminate. Additional circumferential layers are placed at wing shear local introductions and above the fuselage bulkheads to improve notched and bearing strength of the skin. To reinforce the cut outs of the load carrying access doors there are also local additional layers of different directions necessary. With all these local additional layers the skin is built from about 570 plies, where only 16 plies cover the whole area.

As mentioned above the monocoque requires stiffening frames. One side of the web has to be flat to allow installations to be attached. A typical cross section is shown in Fig. 4. The frames are inverted J-sections with a tapered foot optimized in width and ply drop off arrangement. The basic lay up is of ± 45 degree plies to carry shear, and interspersed 90 degree plies to increase web buckling stability. Circumferential layers adjusted to the frame bending moments are interleaved in the flange and skin. To soften peak stresses an adhesive layer is placed at the interface of frame and skin. To accommodate fibre direction, the web layers are segmented in five sections (Fig. 5). These segments are layed up flat and hotformed in

four steps to form first a [and a [with interleaved 0-degree plies and then put together to form the J-section.

To produce the monocoque (Fig. 6), the skin with the interleaved longerons is layed up on a male tool and than transferred to the female composite curing tool. The frames are then placed into the mould and fixed at the edges. After bagging the whole monocoque is cured in one single autoclave cycle. Since the edges of the frames and the access panel cut outs are net moulded, only cleaning of excess resin and final trimming of the outside contours is necessary.

3. MATERIAL SELECTION

To save cost for qualification, design allowable data collection and production it was decided to use one common CFRP material. The candidate CFRP material had to be selected considering all structural and manufacturing requirements of the whole aircraft including wings, fuselage and fin. At the time, when the material had to be chosen, carbon fibre thermoplastics technology was not so developed - and is still not - with respect to mechanical properties and manufacturing techniques to justify their application. So the selection concentrated on carbon fibre reinforced thermosets. Weight saving is a major driver in the choice of the best suited material, therefore the influence of the different mechanical properties on the component weights had to be established. For this reason a preliminary stressing of the major structural parts was carried out and the dimensioning criteria and their contribution to the structural weight established

- tensile elastic modulus (for wing and fin efficiency)	7 %
- compression elastic modulus (for efficiency and buckling stability)	40 %
- open hole tension strength	15 %
- filled hole compression strength	22 %
- bearing strength	11 %
- compression after impact strength (additional to above properties)	5 %

Based on the initial data of prepreg suppliers and on preliminary strength tests performed by MBB, a challenging specification, which was however considered to be achievable, was drafted, specifying test conditions and specimen geometry for CFRP prepregs. The major requirements are given in Fig. 7.

Additional requirements were:

- Mechanical properties should not degrade more than 5 percent after being subjected to aggressive fluids e.g. fuel, hydraulic oil, MEK for a certain period.

- Sufficient temperature margin to the wet glass transition temperature.

Weight reductions have to be achieved in a cost effective way, therefore manufacturing requirements have to be considered too.

Besides a long list of basic requirements, regarding health, cure temperature and pressure, exothermal reaction, etc., the key points for ease of manufacturing and cost reduction of large integrally stiffened CFC-structure were:

- The prepreg must not require resin bleed and any debulking.
- Guaranteed shop life of at least 21 days at 27°C/75% RH with no significant loss of tack to allow enough lay-up time for large complex parts.
- The prepreg must be capable for repeated cure cycles for co-curing and co-bonding applications.
- The prepreg must be suitable for automatic tape laying machines.

For final selection three candidate CFRP prepreg systems have been evaluated based on mechanical properties tests and on manufacturing trials on cocured/cobonded parts. Fig. 7 shows the achievements of the strength requirements by test results of the candidate CFRP prepreg systems. 5245C from BASF with Torays T800H fibres was chosen because the other systems would have added an estimated weight penalty of 4.6 % and 7.8 % respectively.

4. ANALYSIS AND TESTING

The stress analysis of the centre fuselage monocoque is based on a total aircraft finite element calculation using NASTRAN with substructure technique. The complete model consists of 13 substructures, 18261 nodes, 34700 elements, 72288 degrees of freedom and 110 loadcases. The stressing of the monocoque would by far be outside of the scope of this paper. However, two critical features of the design will be discussed. The first is the buckling stability of the skin and the second is the interface strength of frames to skin.

Due to lack of experience, especially with respect to the fatigue behaviour, in the past CFRP-structures have been stressed to be free of buckling up to ultimate load. A significant weight saving can be achieved if this design practice is relaxed.

With respect to buckling stability the monocoque skin can be subdivided into subpanels with the boundaries at fuselage bulkheads and longitudinal substructure members. A typical panel has a length of about one meter in flight direction and a circumferential length of about 1.3 meter. The panel is stiffened with frame stiffeners and is loaded by longitudinal and circumferential compression stresses and shear stresses. Comprehensive analyses, supported by tests, were carried out to determine on flat cocured stiffened shear and compression panels of different thicknesses, ply orientation and stacking sequence the start of initial buckling, fatigue behaviour and residual

strength after impact. Fig. 8 shows the load carrying capability of a shear panel with the a relatively low stability limit and a high failure load. Fig. 9 presents a similar characteristic for compression loaded panels with nonlinear strain increases beyond stability. Several shear and compression panels have been fatigue tested at environmental conditions up to 100°C under a FALSTAFF load spectrum for 18000 simulated flight hours with a maximum fatigue load well above the stability limit, Fig. 10 and Fig. 11. At a subsequent residual strength test the failure loads of the panels have been equal or above the static failure loads. All panels failed after the separation of the stiffeners from the skin.

Based on the above test and analysis results it was decided to design the skin with buckling from limit load on. This assumption is still on the safe side but justified that the stability limit is underpredicted by analysis. To finally prove the design for a curved skin under biaxial loads, tests have been carried out on rather large representative stiffened skins mounted on metal boxes (Fig. 12). Again a finite analysis to calculate internal stresses and buckling behaviour was carried out. Fig. 13 shows the buckling deformations of the monocoque confirmed by Moire measurements on the test box (Fig. 14).

The interface plane of the skin to the cocured stiffening frames is in principle loaded by shear and pull-off forces and has also to withstand the straining of the skin across the stiffener foot. The load carrying capability of this interface is purely dependent on the bond strength. The maximum stresses in the foot area are very much influenced by the shape and of the foot and by the quality of the manufactured shape of the filler material in the gap of the foot radii. Various studies on neat resin, twisted glass and carbon tows for the filler material and on foot geometry with constant thickness, constant thickness with overlayers, various foot width and with and without stress relieving adhesives have been investigated by analysis and tests. The finally used configuration (see cut-up on Fig. 15) shows a tapered foot with 62 mm width, and a ± 45 degree laminate gap filler, and an adhesive around the gap filler and between skin and frame foot. Fig. 16 shows a finite element analysis model of the chosen design to determine pull-off strength. Using von Mises as failure criterion for the adhesive and a modified Tsai-Hill criterion for the CFRP-layers the pull off strength of the stiffening frames has been determined. A picture of a typical failure surface of T-pull specimen is shown on Fig. 17. Three dimensional finite element analyses have been carried out using the above failure criteria to establish the shear carrying capability and the interaction of shear- and pull off strength. A comparison of analyses and test results is given in Fig. 18.

5. WEIGHT AND PRODUCTION COST ASPECTS

The weight of the monocoque with the presented design is 128 kg and by analytical comparison to a metal structure a weight saving of 32% was calculated. Weight reductions have to be achieved in a cost effective way. The production cost of a structural component may be broken down into raw material cost, single part manufacture cost and assembly cost. Fig. 19 shows a comparison of these cost factors to metal structures. As composite materials are more expensive than metals, detail part

manufacture is about comparable, the assembly costs have to be reduced drastically to build a cost effective structure. This is only achievable by a considerable reduction in the number of detail parts and mechanical fasteners by higher part integration. Fortunately high part integration contributes also to a weight saving. With the presented monocoque design high part integration is achieved by cocuring skin and stiffeners in one single cure cycle. Demonstrated detail part reductions of MBB built airframe components are given in Fig. 21. By this design the number of detail parts is reduced by a factor of 3.4 and the number of mechanical fasteners by a factor of 2.5. Even so the component itself does cost more than a metal structure the CFRP monocoque is cost effective if life cycle cost are considered also.

6. CONCLUSION

It is demonstrated, that a high weight saving at effective production cost can be achieved for future fighter aircraft centre fuselages by cocuring all the monocoque structure in one single cure cycle and that the strength can reliably be predicted.

FIG. 1 STRUCTURAL ARRANGEMENT CENTRE FUSELAGE

FIG. 2 TYPICAL LONGERON CROSS SECTION

FIG. 3 SKIN SCHEME AND REINFORCEMENTS

FIG. 4 MONOCOQUE STIFFENING FRAME

FIG. 5 FRAME CROSS SECTION AND LAY-UP

FIG. 6 CURED MONOCOQUE

		Require- ment	Material 5245C/T800	Material B	Material C
Tension Modulus	[N/mm ²] ¹⁾	165000	167000	159100	154700
Compression Modulus	[N/mm ²] ¹⁾	150000	147000	146400	141250
Open Hole Tension Strength	[N/mm ²] ¹⁾	550	545	433	473
Filled Hole Compression Strength	[N/mm ²] ¹⁾	350	395	402	366
Bearing Strength	[N/mm ²] ¹⁾	900	881	914	861
CAI	[ρm/m]	4200	4050	4029	4267

¹⁾ Test temperature range from -55°C to 100°C and equilibrium moisture content at 85% RH/70°

FIG. 7 COMPARISON OF THE SELECTED MATERIAL TO THE REQUIREMENT AND COMPETITORS

FIG. 8 LOAD/STRAIN DIAGRAM OF A J-STIFFENED SHEAR PANEL

FIG. 9 LOAD/OUT OF PLANE DEFLECTION OF AN J-STIFFENED COMPRESSION PANEL

FIG. 10 STATIC SHEAR STRENGTH AND RESIDUAL STRENGTH AFTER 18000 SIMULATED FLIGHT HOURS

FIG. 11 STATIC COMPRESSION STRENGTH AND RESIDUAL STRENGTH AFTER 18000 SIMULATED FLIGHT HOURS

FIG. 12 BUCKLING TEST BOX PRIOR FINAL ASSEMBLY

FIG. 13 PLOT OF BUCKLING SHAPE OF MONOCOQUE SKIN

FIG. 14 MOIRE BUCKLING PATTERN

FIG. 15 COCURED INTERFACE OF FRAME TO SKIN

FIG. 16 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL TO DETERMINE INTERFACE STRESSES OF FRAME TO SKIN

FIG. 17 FAILURE SURFACE OF FRAME TO SKIN INTERFACE

FIG. 18 T-PULL/SHEAR STRENGTH OF FRAME/SKIN INTERFACE

	Metal		CFRP	
	Parts	Fasteners	Parts	Fasteners
Tornado CFRP Taileron	422	5000	104	2150
Test Front Fuselage	1650	8000	258	1050
Airbus Rudder	600	17015	335	4800
Airbus Fin	2072	42000	96	3600
CFRP Centre Fuselage	194	9280	38	2408

FIG. 19 EFFECT OF STRUCTURAL INTEGRATION AND MATERIAL COSTS ON PRODUCTION COSTS

FIG. 20 DEMONSTRATED STRUCTURAL INTEGRATION AT MBB

